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DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH HERNIAS OF THE LUMBAR SPINE AND ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE**Sultonov A.***Doctor of Medical Sciences, senior researcher, JSC "NMMC" MA "Kyzyl-Kum", Deputy Director for Personnel and Administrative Issues, Republic of Uzbekistan
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8216-54>***Rakhimbaeva G.***Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor Head of the Department of Nervous Diseases of the Tashkent Medical Academy, Republic of Uzbekistan***Mirzaev A.***neurosurgeon, department of neurosurgery, multidisciplinary clinic, Tashkent Medical Academy, Republic of Uzbekistan.*ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-8664-5939><https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13620409>**Abstract**

The article of data on the effectiveness of modern methods of treatment of intervertebral hernias of the lumbar spine is presented. Historical aspects of the development of spinal neurosurgery, the main methods of surgical treatment. This publication presents the main methods of surgical treatment of herniated intervertebral disc, characterizes the positive and negative aspects of each method. A differentiated approach to the treatment of intervertebral disc herniations in the lumbar spine. Assessment of quality of life and pain syndrome using questionnaires. Determining the effectiveness of surgical treatment and the impact on the quality of life of patients.

Keywords: diagnostics, herniated disc, surgical treatment, conservative treatment, differentiated an approach.

Relevance

According to literature, osteochondrosis develops due to a lack of calcium salts, which in turn causes fragility, degenerative changes in cartilage, bones throughout the human body, in the process of restoring degenerative changes, calcium salts accumulate in these areas and then the spinal column deforms, forming a kind of vicious circle. Due to the accumulation of calcium salts, intervertebral discs lose their elasticity; improper physical activity, even minor, can cause a rupture of the fibrous ring, intervertebral disc, and the pulp part of the disc comes out through the destroyed area, forming a hernia [4,7,8].

If we analyze the literature, it becomes clear that most often, herniated intervertebral discs occur at the lumbar level, about 65%, less often - at the cervical level, about 30%, very rarely up to 5% - in the thoracic spine. The reason for the least occurrence of intervertebral hernias in the thoracic spine is due to the fact that the rib cage is formed by the rib cage, which is a kind of support for the thoracic vertebrae. Men suffer from intervertebral disc hernias slightly more often than women [8,11,13]. The disease is more common in people of working age 25-55 years. Often the disease is associated with the type of work of people and professional activity [8,11,13].

The issue of choosing the tactics of surgical treatment, including both the choice of surgical intervention itself, depending on the damage to the intervertebral discs, their duration and the involvement of other concomitant pathologies in the process can be different [2,6,12].

Depending on the location of the intervertebral disc protrusion in relation to the spinal canal, foraminal

opening, and spinal cord structures, central, posterolateral, paramedian, total, foraminal, and extreme lateral are distinguished [1,3,9]. According to literature data, posterolateral 53% and paramedian 33% intervertebral disc herniations are more common in practice. They occupy the lateral part of the spinal canal, exerting pressure on the corresponding spinal nerve root, which is manifested by reticular syndrome on the ipsilateral side in the clinical picture. Foraminal or lateral intervertebral disc herniation 3% goes into the intervertebral opening, where it directly compresses the spinal nerve root, which is manifested by monoradicular syndrome on the ipsilateral side [3,9,13].

Currently, the quality of life is assessed by various scales and questionnaires. For a full study of the quality of life of patients, it is of great importance to assess the overall quality of life, quality of life by disease and symptom of the disease [5,10].

Thus, the issue of differentiated surgical treatment of intervertebral disc herniations remains not fully resolved. Pain syndrome that occurs with intervertebral disc herniations dramatically reduces the quality of life of patients.

Purpose of the study: improving the treatment results of patients with lumbar spine hernias by using differentiated treatment tactics with an assessment of the quality of life.

Material and methods

The study is based on the results of observations of 165 patients with lumbar pain who were treated in the hospital of the Tashkent Medical Academy, a multidisciplinary clinic, and the neurosurgery department from 2019 to 2023.

To establish a diagnosis and choose a treatment method, all patients underwent a comprehensive examination, including clinical, neurological and instrumental research methods.

During the initial examination of patients, the following symptoms were taken into account as the main criteria for lumbar osteochondrosis (LO) - unilateral or, in rare cases, bilateral pain in the lumbar region radiating to the leg; the presence of sensitivity disorders in the innervation zone of any roots of the lumbar vertebrae; the presence of symptoms such as hypertonicity of the lumbar muscles due to pain syndrome; limited movement due to pain syndrome or paresis of the limbs; atrophy of the leg muscles in the innervation zone of the roots of the lumbar vertebrae were also checked.

An important place in establishing a diagnosis and determining further treatment tactics is given to magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data from 1.5 to 3.0 Tesla, MSCT and digital X-ray research methods.

In our studies, questionnaires were used to assess the quality of life of patients: the European Quality of Life Questionnaire Euro Qol-5D and a visual analogue scale (VAS) to determine the intensity of pain. After diagnosis, all patients were subjected to surgical intervention or conservative treatment by determining the tactics of increasing the radicality of pain syndrome and signs of root damage

Results and discussion

The results of observations of 165 patients with lumbar pain who were treated in the hospital of the Tashkent Medical Academy, a multidisciplinary clinic, and the neurosurgery department in the period from 2019 to 2023 were studied.

All patients were divided into three groups according to the treatment methods, severity of the pain syndrome of lumbar osteochondrosis and the state of their somatic status.

The first group included 53 (32.2%) patients who underwent conservative treatment, blockades, physiotherapy and other methods of treatment. The second group included 55 (33.3%) patients who underwent endoscopic methods of allocating a herniated disc between the 4-5 and 5-1 sacral vertebrae of the lumbar spine. The third group consisted of 57 (34.5%) patients who underwent surgery to remove a herniated disc using an intralaminar approach.

By age, patients were distributed according to the WHO classification, which provides for the allocation of age groups: young age 14-19 years; younger middle age 20-44 years; older middle age 45-59 years; elderly age 60-74 years; old age 75-89 years; In our observations, patients were aged from 24 to 79 years.

Distribution of patients by age and gender showed that among the patients, men predominated - 116 (70.2%), and women - 49 (29.8%), which is associated with the physical exertion of men during work. Most patients 68 (41.5%) of older middle and old age, the maximum number of patients fell on the age group of 60-74 years, 50 (30.4%), which is consistent with the data of world scientists.

When examining the somatic status, it was revealed that among 165 patients, 67 (40.5%) patients

had somatic pathology, manifested in the form of arterial hypertension in 51 (31.0%) patients, ischemic heart disease in 13 patients (7.8%). In 18 (11.2%) cases diabetes mellitus was noted, in 4 (2.6%) patients liver pathology and in 1 (0.9%) renal failure. It should be noted that in one and the same patient a combination of two or more somatic diseases was noted, this was especially typical for cardiovascular diseases.

In our studies, 112 (67.8%) of 165 patients underwent surgical treatment, the indications for surgical treatment were: cauda equina syndrome with increasing dysfunction of the pelvic organs and radiculo-ischemic manifestations; duration of radicular pain syndrome or pain in the lumbar region for at least 4 weeks; herniated disc of any localization, but only at one level, confirmed by MRI with axial sections; lack of effect from conservative treatment.

Neurological symptoms in the second and third groups in total 173 cases, they could combine several symptoms at once in one patient in both groups. The most frequent complaint presented by patients in the second and third groups was pain in the lumbar spine (38 cases), the second most frequent complaint was gait disturbance and sensory disturbance (36 cases each), the third most frequent complaint was a forced body position due to pain syndrome (27 cases).

Analysis of the level of damage to the roots of the equine tail in the study of 165 patients showed the following results, twice as many observations at the level of LV-SI 106 (64.3%) compared to LIV-LV 59 (35.7%), this is due to the greatest load on the lumbar spine associated with a low-mobility sacrum.

Positive results among the 165 patients studied were noted in 156 (95.6%), without changes in 9 (5.4%). The indicators in all 3 groups were good since a differentiated approach to the treatment of patients with lumbar pain is always justified.

This proves the effectiveness of treatment methods for patients with lumbar hernias with a differentiated approach.

A study of the quality of life of 165 patients was achieved using the European Quality of Life Questionnaire EuroQol-5D and a visual analogue scale (VAS) to determine the intensity of the pain syndrome. In all the study groups, the most significant deterioration of the EuroQol-5D questionnaire parameters was pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression. The study of the quality of life (QOL) of patients in all groups was conducted before and after surgical treatment.

Analysis of the results of the study of the quality of life (QOL) of 165 patients showed that the data obtained in all three groups were different, the deterioration of the QOL indicators of the first group did not differ much from normal, in the second group it was revealed that the QOL indicators of patients moderately worsened, in the third group this indicator of the QOL of patients worsened greatly and slowly recovered, this is due to the course of the disease and degenerative changes in osteochondrosis of the spine with concomitant somatic pathology.

Descriptor's pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression deviated from the norm to a greater extent in the second and third groups and slowly recovered, the QOL

indicators of patients in the first group returned to normal immediately after surgical treatment.

A study of 165 patients showed that the QOL parameters pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression suffer the most, which is facilitated by the emotional state of patients.

Pain syndrome as a strong irritant primarily affects the emotional state of patients, being a provoking factor in the deterioration of the QOL of patients.

For a full assessment of the QOL of patients, it is necessary to use two or more questionnaires covering more impaired descriptors and indicators. To study the parameters of pain syndrome, we used a scale (VAS) for the completeness of the study. VAS scores before surgery revealed mild pain (1-3 points) in 20 (37.7%) patients in the first group, moderate pain (4-6 points) in 7 (13.2%), mild pain in 21 (38.2%) patients in the second group, moderate pain in 33 (60%), very severe pain (7-9 points) in one patient, unbearable pain (10 points) in one patient, mild pain in 6 (11%) patients in the third group, moderate pain in 42 (73.6%), very severe pain in 8 (14%), and unbearable pain in 1 (2%) patient.

After surgery, pain syndrome regressed to disappearance in all three groups, mild pain persisted only in two patients in the first group, one patient in the second group, and four patients in the third group, which proves the effectiveness of treatment methods with a differentiated approach.

The visual scale and its five parameters allow a more detailed examination of the pain syndrome, no pain (0 points), mild pain (1-3 points), moderate pain (4-6 points), very severe pain (7-9 points), unbearable pain (10 points), which means the maximum possible version of the sensation of pain syndrome.

Thus, the restriction of movement, the inability of patients to engage in everyday work sharply reduces social existence and adaptation in the living environment. A long process of rehabilitation and pain syndrome exhausts the nervous system in most patients, causing emotional even after the disorder and depressive syndrome, which persists for a long time even after recovery.

Conclusions:

1. Distribution of patients by age and gender showed that among the patients there were predominantly men (116 (70.2%)), and women - 49 (29.8%), which is associated with the physical exertion of men during work. The majority of patients 68 (41.5%) were of older middle and old age, the maximum number of patients fell on the age group of 60-74 years, 50 (30.4%), which is consistent with the data of world scientists.

2. In our studies, 112 (67.8%) of 165 patients underwent surgical treatment, the indications for surgical treatment were: cauda equina syndrome with increasing dysfunction of the pelvic organs and radiculo-ischemic manifestations; duration of radicular pain syndrome or pain in the lumbar region for at least 4 weeks; herniated disc of any localization, but only at one level, confirmed by MRI with axial slices; lack of effect from conservative treatment.

3. Positive results among the 165 patients studied were noted in 156 (95.6%), without changes in 9

(5.4%). The indicators in all three groups were good, since a differentiated approach to the treatment of patients with lumbar pain is always justified.

4. The VAS scores before surgery revealed mild pain (1-3 points) in 20 (37.7%) patients in the first group, moderate pain (4-6 points) in 7 (13.2%), mild pain in 21 (38.2%) patients in the second group, moderate pain in 33 (60%), very severe pain (7-9 points) in one patient, unbearable pain (10 points) in one patient, mild pain in the third group in 6 (11%), moderate pain in 42 (73.6%), very severe pain in 8 (14%), and unbearable pain in 1 (2%) patient.

5. A study of 165 patients showed that the QOL parameters that suffer the most are pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression, which is facilitated by the emotional state of patients.

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